

S3E CHARGE ACCELERATOR PROGRAM

INVESTOR PORTFOLIO

**MEET THE TOP 17 DEEP TECH
STARTUPS IN SOUTHERN EUROPE**

Funded by
the European Union

LIST OF STARTUPS

- **ELENAV.AI** Safer & high-tech navigation systems
- **DATAFRUIT** IIOT platform for automated & sustainable manufacturing
- **MOVEN** Mobility Ventures
- **BEDEV** Early stage medical devices using 3D printing
- **CRIAM** Portable blood testing device for reliable, on-the-spot diagnostics.
- **QX** Web3 Customer Experience and Loyalty for Brands and Smart Cities
- **IVOLUNTRY** The digitization of volunteering
- **ECOBUBBLE** Pollution-eating design and AI-based maintenance
- **ORBIBA ROBOTICS** An Organic Bond Robotics Technology for Farmers
- **EXRCISER** XR Health & Wellness Technology

Click ➤ and go directly to the startup's information

LIST OF STARTUPS

- **BAUKUNST** Heritage preservation through 3D and Augmented Reality
- **INTELLECTRA** Transforming wireless technologies to safeguard digital infrastructures
- **ROSEY'S MARK** Unveiling the powerful properties of the Bulgarian rose
- **NANOMIK** Biochemistry leading change in life sciences
- **INNERVOICES** Unlocking the wisdom within through deep tech and social science research
- **ENTOPROTEIN** Changing the World of Food, One Insect at a Time
- **BOMENSOFT** R&D for internet of things, deep learning and machine learning

SAFER & HIGH-TECH NAVIGATION SYSTEMS

elnav.ai

Founded in 2021 and based in Split, Croatia, ELNAV.AI offers a significant competitive advantage in the maritime industry by enhancing communication and reducing navigational errors, thanks to their AI-powered monitors and radars. By introducing their revolutionary technology, they aim to become a leader in maritime safety technology by reducing navigation related incidents at sea.

COUNTRY CROATIA

SECTOR MARITIME

INVESTMENT NEEDED 920,000 €

HRVOJE MIHOVILOVIĆ
Founder & CEO

IVAN BILIŠKOV
Software Development

MISLAV BIONDIĆ
Marketing Manager

IIOT PLATFORM FOR AUTOMATED & SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING

datafruit.eu

Founded in 2022 and based in Sofia, Bulgaria, DataFRUIT is building an integrated platform powered by Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) to enable automated manufacturing across various sectors, including: energy, construction, logistics and transport. By optimising processes and systems across the production line, DataFRUIT also helps industrial manufacturers adopt more sustainable practices.

COUNTRY BULGARIA

SECTOR MANUFACTURING

INVESTMENT NEEDED TBD

STANIMIR JOVCHEV
Founder & CEO

MIGLENA DOĞAN
Head of Marketing, Sales & Bussines Dev

MOVEN: MOBILITY VENTURES

moven.pro

MOVEN has the mission of accelerating the shift towards sustainable cities democratizing access to high quality data and AI capabilities for good decision making. MOVEN offer a data insight marketplace for sustainable cities focused on applying the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to accurately analyse data from a variety of sources, such as data spaces, and data from both public and private. Our platform empowers individuals, enterprises, and governmental entities with the insights necessary to make informed decisions in urban mobility and transportation planning.

COUNTRY

SPAIN

SECTOR

MOBILITY

INVESTMENT NEEDED

300,000 €

SERGIO DIEZ

Founder & CEO

INMACULADA CABALLERO

Innovation Manager

[linkedin.com/bedev](https://www.linkedin.com/company/bedev)

EARLY STAGE MEDICAL DEVICES USING 3D PRINTING

Founded in 2020, Bedev focuses on the development of early stage medical devices using 3D printing. Our approach is to bring medtech closer to a greener perspective, giving medical devices the ability to be environmentally sustainable without risking patient safety.

GONÇALO FONSECA
Founder & CEO

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

INVESTMENT NEEDED

500,000 €

CRIAM KNOWLEDGE

criamknowledge.com

Headquartered in Braga (Portugal), CRIAM follows a clear mission: to ensure every patient that needs help is adequately diagnosed and treated. With this aim in mind, this startup has developed a multi-purpose, electricity independent, easy-to-use and portable single-test Point of Care (PoC) diagnostics tool for rapid, highly accurate, automatized (no human error) and affordable blood testing.

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

INVESTMENT NEEDED

8,000,000 €

VITOR CRESPO

Founder & CEO

LJILJANA DUKANOVIC

Chief Scientific Officer

AFONSO PINHEIRO

Researcher

WEB3 CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE AND LOYALTY FOR BRANDS AND SMART CITIES

qx.ventures

QX is a technology company committed to transforming customer experiences and loyalty for brands, retailers, and shopping centers worldwide. Our international team of experts and consultants brings deep insights and extensive experience in implementing the latest innovations in user-friendly and seamless ways. We excel in integrating technologies like blockchain and decentralized systems to enhance customer interaction and loyalty programs.

PLAY ME

ZORAN NASTESKI

Co-Founder & CEO

COUNTRY

NORTH MACEDONIA

SECTOR

SMART CITIES

INVESTMENT NEEDED

500,000 €

IVOLUNTRY

ivoluntry.com

The digitization of volunteering is a tool with which groups will have flexibility and autonomy to publish important information in an online space and will be able to interact with the public while volunteers will be able to have valid and immediate information, gaining time and rewards.

COUNTRY GREECE

SECTOR SOCIAL

INVESTMENT NEEDED TBD

ANDREAS KOUNTOURAS
Founder & CEO

ERRIKA ZELER
Communication Manager

ANTYPAS AZOIDIS
Chief Technology Officer

POLLUTION-EATING DESIGN AND AI-BASED MAINTENANCE

plantiverse.it

Ecobubble is a GreenTech startup advancing sustainable agriculture through smart and plant-driven technology. They're the minds behind Plantiverse, a green area monitoring and management platform designed upon a set of 'plant-driven' and patented methods and systems, which dynamically monitor and optimize automation actions based on the vegetative states of plants and the surrounding environment.

COUNTRY ITALY

SECTOR AGRICULTURE

INVESTMENT NEEDED TBD

NICOLA NESCATELLI
Co-Founder

FEDERICO DI VINCENZO
Co-Founder

AN ORGANIC BOND ROBOTICS TECHNOLOGY FOR FARMERS

orbibarobotics.com

Orbiba stands for "an organic bond." Our basic philosophy is the idea that "People become what they eat". In order to contribute to the field of clean agriculture, Orbiba Robotics utilizes agricultural technology to produce affordable robot platforms. Our goal is to support organic agriculture practitioners who take the initiative to solve the issue of access to safe food, which is becoming increasingly prevalent around the world, by designing and building small robots that have a minimal carbon footprint, utilize renewable energy, and are affordable and high-return on investment.

COUNTRY

TURKEY

SECTOR

AGRICULTURE

INVESTMENT NEEDED

500,000 €

PLAY ME

ILKER BEKTAS

Founder & CEO

MURAT CAN DEMIRAL

Chief Technology Officer

exrciser.com

EXRCISER: REALITY IS NOT ENOUGH

eXRciser brings health and wellness through specialized, immersive and gamified exercises using cutting-edge technology. We provide a service that integrates health under the whole concept of wellness, via a rewarding physical experience (physically, socially and mentally), based on a dynamic open platform which evolves with technology. The goal: help people to live a human experience through physical activity, maximizing correlation –through convolutional analysis- among our AI emotional prediction algorithm, sensor data and user’s experience.

COUNTRY SPAIN

SECTOR HEALTH

INVESTMENT NEEDED 300,000 €

FRANCISCO ROS
Co-Founder

MANUEL PASAMONTES
Chief Technology Officer

BAUKUNST

baukunst.es

Baukunst Arquitectura and Patrimonio Virtual is an innovative company in heritage preservation, renowned for its expertise in 3D digitization and Augmented Reality applications. By combining cutting-edge technology with a conservation-centric approach, Baukunst leads initiatives that transform monuments and heritage sites into immersive digital experiences. Its vision embraces the intersection of tradition and modernity, providing solutions that transcend temporal boundaries, fostering appreciation, and understanding of historical heritage.

COUNTRY SPAIN

SECTOR CULTURE

INVESTMENT NEEDED 500,000 €

ADOLFO IBAÑEZ
Founder & CEO

DAVID CERVERA
Chief Technology Officer

SEBASTIAN JANS
Chief Development Officer

INTELLIGENT SPECTRUM ANALYTICS

intellectra.co

Intellectra is at the forefront of transforming wireless technologies to safeguard and support the wirelessly interconnected digital infrastructure of the future. Our mission is to reshape the wireless cybersecurity landscape by offering cutting-edge solutions tailored to safeguard critical industries and sectors from emerging wireless threats. Leveraging modern technologies such as Machine Learning and privacy-preserving machine learning, we deliver innovative and robust cybersecurity solutions that ensure the resilience and security of wireless networks in an increasingly connected world.

COUNTRY

CYPRUS

SECTOR

SMART CITIES

INVESTMENT NEEDED

220,000 €

CHRISTOS MAVRIDES

Chief Operating Officer

MICHALIS KYRIACOU

CEO

MICHALIS CHRISTOU

Chief Technology Officer

EDIBLE ROSES FOR WELL-BEING

roseysmark.com

Rosey's Mark uses the precious Bulgarian rose flower as a valuable multi-purpose ingredient to create high quality, clean label functional food products. With science-proven functional effects related to anti-stress, digestion, immune system, beauty and anti-aging, Bulgarian rose manifests itself as an edible flower that may efficiently support the modern well-being of the conscious consumers around the world. And do so in the most sustainable and non-invasive way, through daily food habits.

COUNTRY

BULGARIA

SECTOR

HEALTH

INVESTMENT NEEDED

300,000 €

ROSITSA PAUNOVA

Co-Founder & Marketing Manager

INA (PAUNOVA) ABADJIEVA

Co-Founder & Managing Partner

BIOCHEMISTRY LEADING CHANGE IN LIFE SCIENCES

nanomik-tech.com

Nanomik, develops & produces microencapsulated biopesticides for food and agricultural products that protects them against food spoilage without changing their quality. With our proprietary technologies, we develop solutions for Crop Protection, Food preservation and green construction. The leading R&D team of Nanomik has specialized in formulation development, new bio-molecule discovery, bio-engineering of microorganisms and process development for bio-manufacturing.

COUNTRY

TURKEY

SECTOR

AGRICULTURE

INVESTMENT NEEDED

2,800,000 €

BUSE BERBER ÖRÇEN

Co-Founder & COO

ARDA ÖRÇEN

Co-Founder & CTO

ASLI ERDOĞ

R&D Manager

INNERVOICES: UNLOCK THE WISDOM WITHIN

innervoices.ai

Innervoices is a revolutionary app designed to unlock the wisdom within. By providing personalised insights and guidance, it empowers individuals to navigate life's dilemmas and embrace their true selves. Through cutting-edge technology and social science research, Innervoices fosters deep connections to one's inner voices, transforming self-discovery and paving the way to an authentic, fulfilling life.

COUNTRY SPAIN

SECTOR SOCIAL

INVESTMENT NEEDED TBD

MEL AWASI
Co-Founder

MAJA ZAVRŠNIK
CMO & Co-founder

ANALIZZ PARDO TARABAY
Chief Marketing Officer

CHANGING THE WORLD OF FOOD, ONE INSECT AT A TIME

entoprotein.eu

EntoProtein pioneers insect farming in Greece, specializing in crickets for a variety of purposes, providing innovative solutions for human consumption, pet food, livestock, and aquaculture. Our cricket-based products offer a tasty and sustainable alternative to conventional protein sources like whey protein, flour, protein bars, and beverages. By using cricket frass as organic fertilizer, we complete the cycle, enriching soil health and boosting crop yields. Join us in fighting food shortage and climate change with our smart, simple, and delicious protein options.

COUNTRY GREECE

SECTOR AGRICULTURE

INVESTMENT NEEDED TBD

GEORGE RODOPOULOS
Founder & CEO

ALEXANDROS SIMALIDIS
Founder & COO

LAZAROS TSOUROUKIDIS
Chief Development Officer

THEODOROS KOUMIS
Board Member Advisor

BOMENSOFT: AI TECHNOLOGIES

bomensoft.com

Turkish startup Bomensoft Computer Technologies is specialised in artificial intelligence technologies. It operates as an R&D company, conducting research and leading on designs around AI-related concepts such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning.

COUNTRY **TURKEY**

SECTOR **IOT**

INVESTMENT NEEDED **TBD**

BORA OZDEMIR
Founder & CEO

ÖMER MUTLU
AI Team Lead

24 APRIL 2024

OPEN DAY

MEET THE TOP 17 DEEP TECH STARTUPS IN SOUTHERN EUROPE

REGISTER HERE

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the European Union**